

Ditelluratoargentate (III) Diperiodatocuprate (III) and Ditelluratocuprate (III) Solutions in Microanalysis: Titrimetric Determination of Tartaric and Malonic Acids; Citric, Oxalic and Acetic Acids; and Tartaric, Oxalic, and Acetic Acids in Mixture by Selective Oxidation

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Manuscript received 17 October 1973; revised 16 April 1974; accepted 24 April 1974

Methods for determination of individual ingredients in the admixtures of (i) tartaric and malonic acids, (ii) citric, oxalic, and acetic acids, (iii) tartaric, oxalic and acetic acids have been developed by using ditelluratoargentate (III), diperiodatocuprate (III), and ditelluratocuprate (III) solutions as selective oxidants.

PREPARATION, standardization and other analytical applications of ditelluratoargentate¹ (III) diperiodatocuprate² (III) and ditelluratocuprate³ (III) have been described in our earlier publications. A new approach for the determinations of constituents individually in the combination of acids viz. (i) tartaric and malonic; (ii) citric, oxalic and acetic and (iii) tartaric, oxalic and acetic have been attempted employing ditelluratoargentate(III) and ditelluratocuprate (III) as oxidants in mixture (i); and ditelluratoargentate (III) diperiodatocuprate (III) and ditelluratocuprate (III) in mixtures (ii) and (iii). The selective oxidation of the ingredients by the three oxidants under varying experimental conditions is actually the basis for the individual determination conditions is actually the basis for the individual determination of ingredients present in the three mixtures.

Thus the determination of individual acids in the combination mentioned above upto micro amounts is possible by use of these oxidants.

Experimental

Materials :

Ditelluratoargentate (III), diperiodatocuprate (III) and ditelluratocuprate (III) solutions were prepared and standardized as discussed earlier^{1,2,3}.

All other materials used were of reagent grade.

Procedure :

All the mixture solutions were prepared by taking different concentrations of acids.

(i) Determination of tartaric and malonic acids :

Aliquot of the mixture solution was heated at 80° for 3 hrs with an excess of ditelluratoargentate (III) solution which oxidized only tartaric acid upto carbon dioxide and water stage. The unused excess of the oxidant was estimated back by treating with an excess of arsenite solution¹. Same volume of the mixture solution was boiled with an excess of ditelluratocuprate (III) which oxidized both the acids under investigation upto carbon dioxide and water stage and the remaining ditelluratocuprate (III) was determined by arsenite method³.

Determination of (ii) citric, oxalic and acetic acids; (iii) tartaric, oxalic and acetic acids :

Separate aliquots of the mixtures (ii) and (iii) were treated at 80° for 3 hrs with an excess of ditelluratoargentate(III) which oxidized only citric acid present in mix. (ii) and tartaric acid present in mix. (iii) upto carbon dioxide and water stage. The remaining ditelluratoargentate (III) was estimated iodometrically¹. The same aliquots of the mixtures were boiled separately with an excess of diperiodatocuprate (III) which oxidised citric and oxalic acids (in case of mix. (ii)) and tartaric and oxalic acids (in case of mix. (iii)) upto carbon dioxide and water stage and the remaining solution was titrated as discussed earlier². Again same aliquots of the mixture solutions were boiled with an excess of ditelluratocuprate (III) which oxidized all the acids present in mixture (ii) and (iii) upto carbon dioxide and water stage and the unused ditelluratocuprate (III) in the reaction mixture was determined iodometrically.³

Assessment of the individual ingredients in the mixtures has been made by taking in account the

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TARTARIC AND MALONIC ACIDS

Mixture solution		Ditelluratoargentate (III) solution consumed g. mole $\times 10^6$	Tartaric acid found g. mole $\times 10^6$	Ditellurato-cuprate (III) solution consumed g. mole $\times 10^6$	Malonic acid found g. mole $\times 10^6$
Tartaric acid g. mole $\times 10^6$	Malonic acid g. mole $\times 10^6$				
2.64	3.12	2.63	2.63	5.15	3.14
3.90	4.50	3.90	3.90	7.48	4.47
5.60	5.24	5.62	5.62	9.76	5.20
7.50	6.24	7.53	7.53	12.45	6.19
8.81	7.16	8.83	8.83	14.50	7.11

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF CITRIC, OXALIC AND ACETIC ACIDS

Mixture solution			Ditelluratoargentate(III) solution consumed g.mole $\times 10^6$	Citric acid found g.mole $\times 10^6$	Diperiodato-cuprate(III) solution consumed g.mole $\times 10^6$	Oxalic acid found g.mole $\times 10^6$	Ditellurato-cuprate(III) solution consumed g.mole $\times 10^6$	Acetic acid found g.mole $\times 10^6$
Citric acid g.mole $\times 10^6$	Oxalic acid g.mole $\times 10^6$	Acetic acid g.mole $\times 10^6$						
2.54	1.00	1.20	4.56	2.53	6.59	1.01	7.57	1.22
4.32	1.50	1.50	7.77	4.32	10.80	1.51	12.10	1.62
5.82	2.44	2.12	10.48	5.82	15.30	2.41	17.02	2.15
7.25	3.05	2.92	13.08	7.27	19.17	3.06	21.45	2.88
8.20	4.50	3.24	14.80	8.22	23.80	4.52	26.30	3.18

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF TARTARIC, OXALIC AND ACETIC ACIDS

Mixture solution			Ditelluratoargentate(III) solution consumed g.mole $\times 10^6$	Tartaric acid found g.mole $\times 10^6$	Diperiodato-cuprate(III) solution consumed g.mole $\times 10^6$	Oxalic acid found g.mole $\times 10^6$	Ditellurato-cuprate(III) solution consumed g.mole $\times 10^6$	Acetic acid found g.mole $\times 10^6$
Tartaric acid g.mole $\times 10^6$	Oxalic acid g.mole $\times 10^6$	Acetic acid g.mole $\times 10^6$						
1.55	1.22	2.00	1.56	1.56	4.00	1.23	5.63	2.02
2.42	2.10	3.40	2.42	2.42	6.60	2.09	9.30	3.38
3.00	3.42	5.00	3.00	3.00	9.88	3.44	13.80	4.95
4.23	3.95	7.12	4.24	4.24	12.12	3.94	17.80	7.10
5.14	4.24	8.80	5.12	5.12	13.60	4.20	20.70	8.87

difference in the consumption and equivalence of the oxidants. The experiment has been performed using various concentrations of mixture solution.

Results and Discussion

Tartaric, malonic, citric, oxalic, and acetic acids required 10, 8, 18, 2 and 8 equivalents of the oxidant respectively per g. mole of the acid taken for their complete oxidation to carbondioxide and water stage. The amounts are calculated in g. mole and the experiments has been reported several times

with 10^{-5} - 10^{-6} g. mole of the substance and a deviation in the results was found within $\pm 0.8\%$. Interferences were observed in the presence of foreign inorganic and organic materials.

References

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